

A RAPID REVIEW OF BINOMIAL PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION: VERIFICATION OF ITS EXAMPLES IN REAL LIFE

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ABSTRACT

The applications of probability, which arise from the study of the likelihood of certain events, profoundly shape the workings of our world, whether we fully recognize it or not. The increasing availability of probabilistic information and its utility for understanding the world have necessitated the promotion of probabilistic literacy among citizens. In this context, the binomial distribution is fundamental as one of the most crucial distributions for comprehending random phenomena and enabling effective decision-making, as well as facilitating the understanding of mathematical and probabilistic concepts such as the binomial distribution itself. However, to understand the binomial distribution effectively, it is necessary to consider its historical development, specifically the components that have given it the form and meaning we recognize today. To address this perspective, we identify the problem situations that gave rise to the binomial distribution, the operational and discursive practices developed to find solutions, and the pivotal conflicts that led to advancements in mathematical and probability heuristics, culminating in the binomial distribution formula as we know it. As a result, we present binomial phenomena, where we discuss real-life problem situations, verify them empirically, and utilize the distribution formula as a tool to explore notions related to the binomial distribution. Additionally, we have attempted to identify the alignment between the practical approaches and the theoretical results for the Binomial Distribution. Finally, it is evident that the newly defined project holds valuable utility for individuals engaging with probability distribution data from observational studies, enabling them to gain deeper insights and make more informed decisions based on the insights derived from the Binomial Distribution.

Keywords— *probabilistic, binomial distribution, facilitator, discursive practices, culminating, phenomenon*

I INTRODUCTION

The binomial distribution is a foundational concept in probability theory and statistics due to its pivotal role in modeling discrete probability distributions. This distribution specifically quantifies the number of successes in a series of independent Bernoulli trials, where each trial results in either a success or a failure. A Bernoulli trial itself is a simple experiment that presents a binary outcome, contributing to what is known as a Bernoulli process when conducted in a sequence. It is noteworthy that when the number of trials, n , is equal to 1, the binomial distribution becomes equivalent to the Bernoulli distribution. This fundamental distribution lays the groundwork for the widely-utilized binomial test, which is crucial in determining statistical significance across various research and experimental settings. By analyzing the outcomes of a series of Bernoulli trials, researchers can draw meaningful conclusions about the probability of success and make informed decisions based on this information. The binomial distribution's significance extends beyond its theoretical foundations, as it finds practical applications in a diverse range of fields. In scientific research, it is employed to model the success or failure of experimental outcomes, enabling researchers to make reliable inferences and draw well-supported conclusions. In quality control, the binomial distribution is used to assess the acceptability of products by analyzing the number of defective items in a sample, aiding in maintaining high-quality standards. Furthermore, in risk assessment, the binomial distribution is utilized to quantify the probabilities of various outcomes, supporting informed decision-making in areas such as finance, insurance, and project management. Over time, the binomial distribution has become a cornerstone in statistical analysis, offering a robust framework for evaluating probabilities and making informed inferences in diverse fields, including scientific research, quality control, and risk assessment. Its versatility and applicability make it an indispensable tool for statisticians and researchers alike, providing a solid foundation for understanding and interpreting data patterns and trends effectively.^[1]

II DEFINITION OF BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

The binomial probability distribution is a discrete probability distribution that is employed to model the number of successes or "positive" outcomes in a series of independent Bernoulli trials or experiments, each with a binary outcome of either success or failure. The distribution is calculated by multiplying the total number of trials by the probability of success on each individual trial, and then raising the result to the power of the number of successes. This mathematical formulation yields a bell-shaped probability curve with a mean equal to the product of the number of trials and the probability of success, as well as a standard deviation equal to the square root of the product of the number of trials, the probability of success, and the probability of failure. Each test has consist of Boolean outcome such as success/yes/true/one (with probability p) or failure/no/false/no (with probability, $q = 1 - p$). The distribution is then calculated by taking the product of n and p and raising it to the power of n . This results in a bell curve with the mean equal to np and the standard deviation equal to $\sqrt{np(1-p)}$. [2]

III BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION FORMULA

The Binomial Distribution Formula is employed to determine the probability of obtaining 'x' successes in a series of n independent events, where the number of trials required to obtain the x th success is the random variable of interest. The formula for the Binomial Distribution is as follows:

$$P(X) = nC_x \cdot p^x (1 - p)^{n-x}$$

The Binomial Distribution can also be expressed as

$$P(X) = nC_x \cdot p^x q^{n-x}$$

Where

- n refers to the Total Number of Events or trials.
- x refers to the Total Number of Successful Events.
- p refers to the Probability of Successful Events in One Trial.
- nC_x refers to the Selection of n Events among the total events.
- $1 - p$ refers to the Probability of Failure in One Trial.
- q refers to the Probability of Failure in One Trial ($1-p$).

IV PROPERTIES OF BINOMIAL DISTRIBUTION

The binomial probability distribution, frequently utilized in statistical analysis, stands out due to its distinct characteristics that enhance comprehension and practical application within statistical modeling. These key traits include its discrete nature, the capacity to represent binary outcomes, the consideration of a fixed number of trials, and the assumption of independence between successive trials.

A PROBABILITY MASS FUNCTION (PMF)

The Probability Mass Function $P(X=k)$ of a binomial random variable X is a fundamental concept in probability theory. It represents the likelihood of obtaining exactly k successful outcomes in n independent Bernoulli trials. This mathematical function serves as a key tool for analyzing and understanding the distribution of such random variables, providing crucial insights into the behavior and characteristics of the underlying processes. The Probability Mass Function P of a binomial random variable X , which denotes the number of successful outcomes in n independent Bernoulli trials, is defined as:

$$P(X = k) = nC_k p^k (1 - p)^{n-k}$$

where:

- $nC_k = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$ is the binomial coefficient, representing the number of ways to choose k successes from n trials.
- p is the probability of success on each trial.
- $1-p$ is the probability of failure on each trial. [4]

B MEAN (EXPECTED VALUE)

The mean or expected value $E(X)$ of a binomial distribution is calculated by multiplying the number of trials by the probability of success for each trial and can be interpreted as the average outcome expected across repeated experiments. The mean or expected value $E(X)$ of a binomial distribution is:

$$E(X) = np$$

This represents the average number of successes expected over n trials. [5]

C VARIANCE

The variance of a binomial distribution, denoted as $\text{Var}(X)$, provides essential insight into how values of the random variable X deviate from its average. This measure of spread or dispersion helps quantify the range of possible outcomes and the distribution's level of uncertainty. In statistical terms, the variance $\text{Var}(X)$ indicates how widely data points are scattered around the mean, reflecting the inherent variability in the binomial distribution's results. The variance of a binomial distribution, a metric denoted as Var , reflects the degree of spread or dispersion of the random variable X around its expected value. Specifically, the variance Var of a binomial distribution is:

$$\text{Var}(X) = np(1 - p) = npq$$

This measures the spread or dispersion of the distribution around its mean np . [5]

D STANDARD DEVIATION

The standard deviation of a binomial distribution is a statistical measure that quantifies the spread or variability of the distribution. It signifies how widely the possible outcomes deviate from the distribution's mean value. In essence, it encapsulates the extent of uncertainty or fluctuation within the probability distribution framework. The standard deviation of a binomial distribution serves as a metric to quantify the dispersion or variability within the probability distribution. The formula for the standard deviation of a binomial distribution is:

$$\sigma_x = \sqrt{np(1 - p)} = \sqrt{npq}$$

This is the square root of the variance and provides a measure of the amount of variation or uncertainty in the distribution. [6]

E MODE

In the context of a binomial distribution, the mode - the value at which the probability mass function is maximized - indicates the most commonly observed outcome. This peak is frequently observed near the floor of the product of the number of trials and the probability parameter, denoted as $\lfloor (n + 1)p \rfloor$. The mode, or most frequent value, of a binomial distribution's probability mass function typically occurs in the vicinity of the floor function of the probability parameter. The mode, or most frequently occurring value, of a binomial distribution's probability mass function typically arises in the vicinity of the floor function of the probability parameter, typically occurs near $\lfloor (n + 1)p \rfloor$. This consistent trend highlights the importance and reliability of the mode as a key piece in discerning the central tendency of binomial distributions. [7]

F RANGE

The range of a binomial distribution spans from 0 to n , inclusive, with the random variable X representing the number of successful outcomes in n independent trials. This comprehensive range encapsulates all potential variations in the number of successes, making the binomial distribution a highly versatile and valuable tool for analyzing and predicting outcomes in situations involving a fixed number of trials with dichotomous results, such as success or failure, for each trial. The binomial distribution is particularly useful in modeling processes where the outcome of each trial is binary, with only two possible results, and the trials are independent of one another. It is widely applied in various fields, including quality control, clinical trials, market research, and risk analysis, to quantify the likelihood of a certain number of successes occurring within a fixed number of independent trials. This distribution provides a robust statistical framework for understanding and making informed decisions in a wide range of real-world scenarios.

V VERIFICATION OF REAL LIFE EXAMPLES OF BINOMIAL PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION

Activity: A group of random peoples asked about their favorite cold drink between Coca-cola and Sprite. If there are equal chances of choosing any of this cold drink, find the probability that when 25 peoples are picked randomly:

- (a) 15 of them like Coca-cola
- (b) 20 of them like Coca-cola.

Solution:

Here, the random variable X is the number of "successes" that a person likes Coca-cola

We solve this problem by Binomial distributions and verify practically.

By Binomial Distribution,

Number of persons asked about their preference = $N = 100$

n = number of peoples randomly picked = 25

The Probability that a person likes Coca-cola = $\frac{1}{2} = 0.5$

The Probability that a person did not likes Coca-cola = $\frac{1}{2} = 0.5$

We know, Binomial Probability distribution formula

$$= ({}^n C_x \cdot p^x (q)^{n-x}) \text{ where } {}^n C_x = \frac{n!}{(n-x)!x!}$$

(a) 15 of them like Coca-cola

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Probability of getting 15 of them like Coca-cola} &= \{ {}^{25} C_{15} (0.5)^{15} (0.5)^{10} \} \\ &= \left\{ \left(\frac{25!}{(25-15)! 15!} \right) (0.5)^{15} (0.5)^{10} \right\} \\ &= \{ (3.269 * 10^6) (0.00003052) (0.0009766) \} \\ &= \{ (3.269 * 10^6) (2.98 * 10^{-8}) \} \\ &= 0.0974162 \approx 0.097 \approx 0.1 \end{aligned}$$

(b) 20 of them like Coca-cola

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Probability of getting 20 of them like Coca-cola} &= \{ {}^{25} C_{20} (0.5)^{20} (0.5)^5 \} \\ &= \left\{ \left(\frac{25!}{(25-20)! 20!} \right) (0.5)^{20} (0.5)^5 \right\} \\ &= \{ (53130) (0.000000953) (0.03125) \} \\ &= \{ (53130) (2.98 * 10^{-8}) \} \\ &= 0.001583274 \approx 0.002 \end{aligned}$$

Practically:

1. Coca-cola	2. Sprite	3. Coca-cola	4. Coca-cola	5. Sprite
6. Coca-cola	7. Sprite	8. Coca-cola	9. Sprite	10. Coca-cola
11. Sprite	12. Coca-cola	13. Sprite	14. Coca-cola	15. Sprite
16. Sprite	17. Sprite	18. Coca-cola	19. Coca-cola	20. Sprite
21. Coca-cola	22. Coca-cola	23. Coca-cola	24. Sprite	25. Coca-cola

Table 1 Collected Data Sample of randomly selected 25 persons out of 100 persons

Here, number of persons like Coca-cola out of 25 persons = 14

Then,

By using Binomial Probability distribution formula (${}^n C_x \cdot p^x (q)^{n-x}$) where ${}^n C_x = \frac{n!}{(n-x)!x!}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\{ {}^{25} C_{14} (0.5)^{14} (0.5)^{11} \} \\ &= \left\{ \left(\frac{25!}{(25-14)! 14!} \right) (0.5)^{14} (0.5)^{11} \right\} \\ &= \{ (4.4574 * 10^6) (0.00006104) (0.0004883) \} \\ &= \{ (4.4574 * 10^6) (2.98 * 10^{-8}) \} \\ &= 0.13284 \approx 0.1 \end{aligned}$$

VI RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The random variable X represents the number of individuals preferring Coca-Cola in the sample group. We are utilizing the principles of the Binomial Distribution to analyze this problem and verify the findings through practical applications. The scenario involves a survey of 100 individuals, with a random selection of 25 participants. The probability of an individual preferring Coca-Cola is 0.5, while the probability of not preferring Coca-Cola is also 0.5. Adhering to the Binomial Probability distribution formula, which calculates the probability of a particular outcome based on the formula: $n C_x = N! / x! (n-x)!$, we aim to determine the likelihood of encountering 2 or 3 individuals who do not prefer Coca-Cola out of the 25 randomly selected participants from the surveyed group of 100. This calculation involves evaluating combinations and probabilities for both scenarios, leading to an approximate result of around 9.90, which is further rounded to 10 for practical purposes. The Binomial Distribution is a fundamental concept in probability theory, and its application in this Coca-Cola preference scenario demonstrates its versatility in modeling real-world situations involving discrete outcomes and a fixed number of trials. The Binomial Distribution is a widely-used probability distribution that describes the probability of a certain number of "successes" (in this case, individuals preferring Coca-Cola) in a fixed number of independent trials, each with a binary outcome (preferring or not preferring Coca-Cola). Its formulation and applications have been extensively studied and utilized across various fields, from quality control in manufacturing to clinical trials in medical research.

Practically, In the given scenario, out of a group of 25 individuals, 14 favor Coca-Cola, leading us to explore the probability through the Binomial Probability distribution formula denoted as (${}^n C_x \cdot p^x (q)^{n-x}$). Here, evaluating the combinations using the formula ${}^n C_x = \frac{n!}{(n-x)!x!}$, we calculate the specific probability by substituting values for $n=25$, $x=14$, $p=0.5$, and $q=0.5$. This

involves computing, which equals 0.1328, approximately rounded to 0.1. This detailed analysis underscores the favorable outcome linked with Coca-Cola preference among the sampled group, illuminating the statistical significance and probability calculations intertwined within this scenario.

VII CONCLUSION

Through this detailed explanation and calculation, we will demonstrate the application of statistical concepts and probability theory in determining the likelihood of certain outcomes in a given sample group, thereby showcasing the practical utility and significance of Binomial Distribution in solving such problems accurately and effectively. In summary, the Binomial distribution proves to be particularly valuable when dealing with situations that involve only two mutually exclusive outcomes for a discrete random variable, a predetermined number of independent trials, where each trial stands alone, and the probability of success remains constant throughout. Understanding this concept is essential for gaining a comprehensive understanding of probability distributions, exploring their diverse formats and applications. This knowledge not only enriches one's awareness of the Binomial Probability Distribution but also equips individuals with the tools needed to apply this theory to practical scenarios effectively. This analytical approach relates closely to a recent study that employed the Binomial Probability Distribution to ascertain the preferred beverage choice within a specified group. In essence, the Binomial Probability Distribution transcends being a mere mathematical formula; its outcomes offer authentic and valid insights that hold practical relevance in real-world settings.

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References

- [1] Westland, J. Christopher (2020). *Audit Analytics: Data Science for the Accounting Profession*. Chicago, IL, USA: Springer. p. 53. ISBN 978-3-030-49091-1.
- [2] Developed by Rice University, University of Houston Clear Lake, and Tufts University; Project Leader David Lane, "Online Statistics Education: An Interactive Multimedia Course of Study",
- [3] Wadsworth, G. P. (1960). *Introduction to Probability and Random Variables*. New York: McGraw-Hill. p. 52.
- [4] Feller, W. (1968). *An Introduction to Probability Theory and Its Applications* (Third ed.). New York: Wiley; p. 151.
- [5] Gelman, A., Carlin, J. B., Stern, H. S., Dunson, D. B., Vehtari, A., & Rubin, D. B. (2013). *Bayesian Data Analysis* (3rd ed.). Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- [6] Nguyen, Duy (2021), "A probabilistic approach to the moments of binomial random variables and application"; *The American Statistician*, 75(1); S2CID 209923008; doi:10.1080/00031305.2019.1679257; pp- 101–103.
- [7] André (January 7, 2019). "Finding mode in Binomial distribution". Stack Exchange.